

Experimental

The oscillations in the concentration ratio of Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} or Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} were recorded using $x-t$ recorder. Smooth bright platinum was employed as indicator electrode and saturated calomel was used as the reference electrode together with (saturated KNO_3) salt-bridge having a sintered silica disc at the end dipping in the reaction mixture. All the constituents except one (mixture of oxalic acid and acetone) were placed in a glass cell provided with a jacket through which preconditioned water could be passed for studies at various temperatures. The reaction mixture was thoroughly stirred with a magnetic stirrer. When the temperature of the reaction mixture become constant ($\pm 0.1^\circ$), the mixture of oxalic acid and acetone solution thermostated at the same temperature was instantly transferred to the cell as the last addition. The measurements were made at 25, 30, 35 and 40° for Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} .

The composition of the reaction mixture was as follows: H_2SO_4 (1.5M), BrO_3^- (0.02M), oxalic acid (0.03M), acetone (0.45M) and Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} (0.0005M). The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The apparent energy of activation for the overall process was calculated from the slope of the linear plot of $\log(1/t)$ vs $1/T$, on the basis that the rate constant is inversely proportional to the time (t). For this purpose the period of the second oscillation as well as the onset time were considered. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and were dissolved in double-distilled water.

Apparent Energy of Activation of Belousov-Zhabotinskii Reaction with Mixed Organic Substrate

S. M. PASTAPUR and V. R. KULKARNI*

Department of Chemistry, Gulbarga University,
Gulbarga-585 106

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THE study of oscillating chemical reactions has been dominated by the Belousov-Zhabotinskii (BZ) reaction¹. A number of experiments on the BZ reaction has been carried out in which substitutions² were made for inorganic acid, metal ion catalyst and organic materials. The use of a mixture of organic acid and acetone in place of a single organic substrate is one such important modification^{3,4}. One of them is the system⁴ containing BrO_3^- , H_2SO_4 , oxalic acid, acetone and Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} . The present work deals with the determination of the apparent energy of activation of the overall process of the above system.

TABLE 1—SULPHURIC ACID- BrO_3^- -OXALIC ACID-ACETONE- Mn^{II} VALUES OF APPARENT ENERGY OF ACTIVATION

Temp. $T(K)$	$1/T$	Onset time t (s)	$\log(1/t)$	Time period t (s)	$\log(1/t)$
298	3.356×10^{-3}	519	-2.715	43.5	-1.638
303	3.300×10^{-3}	325	-2.511	27.0	-1.431
308	3.247×10^{-3}	212	-2.326	17.5	-1.243
313	3.195×10^{-3}	133	-2.124	12.0	-1.079
E_a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	—	—	16.65	—	16.03

TABLE 2—SULPHURIC ACID- BrO_3^- -OXALIC ACID-ACETONE- Ce^{III} VALUES OF APPARENT ENERGY OF ACTIVATION

Temp. $T(K)$	$1/T$	Onset time t (s)	$\log(1/t)$	Time period t (s)	$\log(1/t)$
298	3.356×10^{-3}	1603	-3.205	44.8	-1.651
303	3.300×10^{-3}	960	-2.982	25.2	-1.401
308	3.247×10^{-3}	600	-2.778	16.0	-1.204
313	3.195×10^{-3}	403	-2.605	9.2	-0.964
E_a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	—	—	17.55	—	19.62

Results and Discussion

From Fig. 1 it is obvious that the Arrhenius equation is valid for the BZ oscillating system containing BrO_3^- , H_2SO_4 , oxalic acid, acetone and Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} in the temperature range investigated. The values of apparent energy of activation obtained for Mn^{II} and Ce^{III} are practically identical, $E_a = 17.1 \pm 0.5$ kcal mol⁻¹ (71.6 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹).

The process of oscillation involves the production of bromine due to the oxidation of oxalic acid by bromate and its consumption by the bromination of acetone⁶. The overall stoichiometry of the reaction may be written as⁵

where RH is acetone.

It can be concluded that the apparent energy of activation of the above oscillating process is not dependent on the nature (for example the redox potential) of the catalyst. The results are in good agreement with the investigations of Körös⁷, who obtained practically the same apparent energy of activation ($E_a = 16.1 \pm 0.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) for the BZ oscillating system containing H_2SO_4 , BrO_3^- , malonic acid and Ce^{III} or Mn^{II} or $\text{Ru}(\text{dipy})_3^{2+}$. Ganapathisubramanian *et al.*⁸ however, reported a different apparent energy of activation for the two catalysts Ce^{III} and Mn^{II} for the BZ system containing malic acid as the organic substrate.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log 1/t$ vs $1/T$ for the onset time of BZ oscillating system containing H_2SO_4 , BrO_3^- , oxalic acid, acetone and Mn^{II} .

Though the above approach is based on a monomolecular treatment⁷ the system as a whole involves a number of steps. In all the above systems bromate and metal catalysts are common while the organic substrates are different. It may be possible that the autocatalytic bursts leading to the production of bromine and oxidised metal species are similar but the later part of the period involving the consumption of bromine and the oxidised metal species are different. A better understanding could be possible if activation energies for various elementary steps were estimated on the lines of the work reported by Kumpinsky *et al.*⁹ for the system $\text{BrO}_3^- - \text{Br} - \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ in continuous stirred tank reactor.

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